

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN DIFFERENT EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of using interactive technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language at a schools. The principal result of our research is the analysis of the influence of using interactive techniques on acquiring communicative competence and personal development. The major conclusions estimate the significance of applying interactive technologies in learning proces

Key words: interactive technology, interactive method, communication, dialogue, discussion, brainstorming, case, project, role play, presentation.

INTRODUCTION. Nowadays, the importance of teaching a foreign language effectively has grown significantly in the world, especially in developing countries, such as Uzbekistan. Foreign language teachers must find ways to increase the level of students' involvement in the process of studying, to raise their motivation for learning languages. One way to reach these goals is using interactive technologies at classes. It helps to develop students' creativity, imagination, increase their cognitive interest in studying foreign languages and improve their communicative skills. The term "interactive learning technology" is usually connected with computer or multimedia learning, as it implies interactive dialogue with real partners and direct exchange of messages. But this notion is wider and means collective cognitive activity where all participants interact, exchange information, solve problems in atmosphere of real collaboration, estimate their own actions. The problem of using the interactive methods of teaching foreign languages at the higher educational establishments was also studied by R. Blair, S. Martinelli, L. Konoplianyk, H. Stern, E. Polat, M. Tailor and others. Interactive learning technologies include clearly planned learning results, interactive methods, tools, and forms stimulating the learning process, cognitive and mental conditions and procedures for achieving planned results. Thus, interactive technology comprises a scope of interactive methods that a teacher uses in his work.

Aims of Foreign Language Teaching at School. As it is mentioned above, there are lots of languages in the world, and some of them fall into the category of international languages or languages of wider communication groups, such as

English, French, German, Spanish, Russian, Italian and Arabic, etc. Learning and teaching a foreign language is very important nowadays. Every day more and more people take up learning a foreign language in order to have an opportunity to get education or job abroad. The knowledge of a foreign language gives the chance to keep up with the latest news and inventions that happen so quickly in the world. In modern society language is used in two ways: orally and in written form. Oral communication implies a speaker and hearer, and written communication implies a writer and a reader.

The practical aims in teaching a foreign language are four in number: hearing, speaking, reading and writing. Knowing the aims is the most important thing in teaching any foreign language. Aims are the first and the most important consideration in any teaching. The process of teaching is very unique and delicate as the learner develops his/her knowledge and passes through every level of professionalism. Hence the teacher should know exactly what his/her pupils are expected to achieve in studying his/her subject, what results he can expect from the pupils at the end of the course, at the end of the year, term, month, week or simply each particular lesson. In other words he should know the aims and objectives of foreign language teaching at schools. The terms 'aims' and 'objectives' should be distinguished clearly. The term 'aim' is mainly used to name the long-term goals (such as reasons for teaching a second language), and 'objectives' are used only for short-term goals (such as goal of a certain lesson).

Practical aims. As subject, the foreign language differs from other subjects which are taught at schools nowadays. For instance, the teaching of history is connected with learning the historical laws and facts which pupils must learn and the teaching of the mother tongue leads to the mastery of the language as a system, (mother tongue is used for communication) so as pupils can employ it more effectively in oral and written speech. It is especially important for pupils to use the foreign language as a means of communication or for receiving and conveying information they need, in a word to use the target language on the same purposes as the native language. In this connection it is appropriate to quote G. Perren: "Whatever a new language is being taught as a curricular extra ... or as an essential medium for education it will be learned by the young child only if it obviously makes possible some purposeful activity other than language learning. If it does not do this, attempts to teach it may be largely a waste of time." (Perren G. *New Languages and Younger Children*. – "English Language Teaching" 1972, No.3, p. 238.) It is common knowledge that

language is used in two ways: directly or orally, and indirectly or in written form. Thus we distinguish oral language and written language. Direct communication requires a speaker and a hearer, indirect communication requires a writer and a reader. The practical aims in teaching a foreign language are four in number: hearing, speaking, reading and writing. The nature of language is important too, as learning a living language implies using the language of sounds, which is speaking. It is not much the ability to speak but rather the oral treatment, the language of sounds, not the graphic signs should serve as a basic means of teaching. The length of the course, the frequency of the lessons, the size of groups should also be taken into consideration in adopting practical aims. The amount of time for language learning is one of the most decisive factors in mastering and maintaining language proficiency since learners need practice. The more time is available for pupils' practice in the target language, the better results can be achieved. In teaching of a foreign language all forms of work and methods should be in close interrelation or else it will be impossible to master the language. However, special attention should be paid mainly to developing of listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. Besides the size of groups should not be too large, usually large groups are divided into two groups. The three major aims that should be reached are reading, speaking and writing which is restricted to teaching the ability to compose simple letters.

The first eight years of school are aimed to the development of speech proficiency, and at the end of this curriculum pupils should be able:

- ✓ to give short talks and carry on conversations upon different topics that are included in the program.
- ✓ to read without a dictionary texts that contain 4-6 unknown words, the meaning of which should be clear from the context or due to familiar word-building elements.

The syllabus for the twelve-year school requires that school-leavers should be able:

- ✓ to read and understand foreign texts with or without dictionary
- ✓ to understand oral language and speak about the topics that are required by the syllabus
- ✓ to write letters.

While teaching a foreign language all types of work must be in close interrelation,

the aim of which is to make possible the mastery of a foreign language. As it is

mentioned above great attention should be paid to practice in hearing, speaking and reading. The achievement of practical aims in foreign language teaching makes possible the achievement of educational and cultural aims.

Educational aims. Learning a foreign language is of great educational value. Through a new language we gain an insight into the way in which words express thoughts, and so achieve greater clarity and precision in our own communications. Even at the most elementary level learning a foreign language teaches the cognizance of meaning, furnishes a term of comparison that gives us an insight into the quality of language. When learning a foreign language the pupil understands better how the language functions and this brings him greater awareness of the functioning of his own language. Language is connected with thinking, through foreign language teaching the teacher has a good opportunity to develop the learner's intellect, his voluntary and involuntary memory, his imaginative abilities and will power. Naturally, in learning a new language the learner has to memorize words, idioms, grammatical structures and keep all these in long-term memory, always ready to use whenever he needs them. Another important factor in language teaching is the learner's imagination, the lack of real communication forces the teacher to create imaginary situations where the learner has to put himself and show his language behavior accordingly.

Teaching a foreign language contributes to the linguistic education of the pupil, the latter extends the knowledge of phonic, graphic, structural, and semantic aspects of languages it is through contrastive analysis of language phenomena.

Cultural Aims. Learning a foreign language gives the learner the opportunity to get acquainted with the life, customs and traditions of the people whose mother tongue is being studied through the different visual or reading materials (movies, cards with views of towns, etc.). Foreign language promotes learner's general educational and cultural growth by enriching their knowledge about foreign countries, and acquainting them with the traditions of the people whose language they study. Through learning a second language the learner gains a deeper insight into the nature and functioning of language as a social phenomenon. The relationship between language and culture is dynamic. Language is an important part of culture. It is the main way which transmits cultural beliefs, values and norms. Language is influenced by culture. Language is one of the most important carriers of culture and reflects the latter.

In conclusion it is proper to say that practical, educational and cultural aims are intimately related and form an inseparable unity. As a matter of facts the leading role is carried with practical aims, for the others can only be achieved through the practical command of the foreign language.

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